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CREATING UNIFIED DESIGN THINKING THROUGH EXPERIENCE MAPPING

Hua Han and Adisorn Supawatanakul
Design Ethnographics, LLC and Conifer Research, LLC
hua@designethnographics.com and adisorn@coniferresearch.com

ABSTRACT

When design meets anthropology, user research uncovers the discrepancies between designers' intended use of products and the everyday practices of cultures and societies. While ethnography has become a powerful observational and data collection tool, designers and researchers often find it challenging to transform instances into behavioral patterns and analytical frameworks so that research findings can live on as actionable design thinking. This article contends that when done collaboratively, experience mapping - a holistic visualization of user experience across time and space - facilitates analysis, and more importantly, helps create a unified front among team members in their understanding of human behaviors and design aspirations.

Keywords: Experience mapping, analytic framework, collaboration, design thinking

DIFFERENT DESIGN THINKING PROCESSES

Design thinking as advocated by consultancies is often packaged as specific *processes*. E-lab's "bowtie model" depicts a 5-stage process: instances, patterns, frameworks, design concepts, and prototyping. Analytic Design Group developed their practices based on a less linear product development process, which the group calls "*Mr. Waterfall meets Mr. Agile*." It emphasizes the importance of rapid iterations (agile) at each stage of product design, the continuity between stages (waterfall), as well as the essence of down-selection (funneling).

SIMILAR CHALLENGES

It is true that design thinking processes have helped formalize the design paradigm by shifting our focus from products to consumer behaviors and to the larger social and economic contexts. However, the job is only half done if we are only proficient in observing but less capable of analyzing what we have seen. Distilling the insights and uncovering opportunity spaces are where the real impacts of design research reside. There are many factors that can potentially lead to an analytical failure, and, therefore, the demise of creative design thinking.

DATA OVERFLOW

"A thick description" (Geertz) is invaluable not only because it explains human behaviors but also their contexts. It creates a large amount of ethnographic data that needs to be systematically processed, shared, analyzed, and stored away. Because the task is time consuming, costly, and can be tedious and anecdotal, we develop "a love-hate relationship" with data. Thus, while a well-done thick description is interesting to read, it can cause adverse impacts on analysis and overwhelm creative thinking.

LACK OF ANALYTICAL TOOLS

Contextual observation and tactical data collection does not necessarily lead to successful designs and marketable products. These days, Post-its, which come in different colors and shapes, are must-haves at workshops. The prolific use of Post-its is such a phenomenon in design research that it's gained a new name - "Post-it porn." Although informational and aesthetically pleasing, seldom are Post-its used properly or "metamorphosed" into creative ideas.

Figure 1, Marilyn Monroe mural made of 'post-its

The benefits of a multidisciplinary research team on diversity of data are well acknowledged. More often than ever, we adopt ensemble interviewing, a technique involving more than one interviewer asking questions. It increases close collaborations between team members in the field and ensures that all important data points are collected. Yet, this emerging technique may create challenges during data collection as well as analysis. For instance, because interviewers may come from different cultural and professional backgrounds, they may feel more compelled to focus on particular topics and information. Other times, interviewers may agree on what they should pay attention to during the interview, but they may not be able to agree on what these observational data really mean.

While ensemble interviewing is helpful, it demands much larger teams in the field, drastically increasing the needs for staffing. When resources are limited, the number of site visits has to be reduced. This being the case, proper techniques for data sharing are even more important to create “collective intelligence” (Bruce Nussbaum), by permitting individual researchers to gain more insights from each other and be familiar with other participants they were not able to visit.

Without good analytical methods and tools that can help generate “creative intelligence,” design research projects often fail to produce real impacts. Instead of having achieved meaningful insights, research teams may walk away from an analysis workshop with fragmented information and seemingly contradictory thoughts illustrated by the following statements:

“Oh, yeah, I observed the same concerns during the interview. But I’m not sure they meant health, balance, and family as you interpreted.”

Marketers: “Perhaps in the next ad we should convey the health benefits instead of balance” (note: balance is an important element in the locals’ beliefs regarding health, yet it is a difficult concept to convey from marketing’s prospective).

Industrial designers: “Maybe we should consider wood furnishing instead of metallic since it looks natural therefore less harmful to families” (note: emphasis on problem-solving through changing furnishing materials but balance is overlooked).

It’s been argued that creativity emerges from shared intelligence, unified thinking, and group activity. Below, we discuss the best use of a visual-behavioral analytical framework - experience mapping - to enhance creative design thinking through shared intelligence and collaboration.

MAPPING EVERYDAY EXPERIENCE

Karen Newman’s (2009) experience mapping contends that one’s past experience does not necessarily constrain his or her future career development. However, the experience mapping exercise we will discuss below is derived from decades of anthropological research about how cultures create and carry out rituals, which are the most highly structured experiences human beings create for one another.

In 1960, anthropologist Arnold Van Gennep first developed the theory on rites of passage, which holds that rituals of transformation such as coming-of-age, graduation, marriage, coronation, and dying undergo the pre-liminal (separation), liminal (transition) and post-liminal (incorporation) phases. Over the years, others have used and built on van Gennep’s original study. For instance, Ben Jacobson, who later found Conifer Research, and his colleagues at Doblin streamlined van Gennep’s original

Figure 2. Experience Mapping: the 5-E framework

classification of the phases so that they are easier to remember and more applicable to the realm of design research. They contend that, similar to the rites of passage, human experiences with any products and services are also transformative, and consist of the following five transitional stages: *Entice, Enter, Engage, Exit, and Extend* (see the 5E model in figure 2). Later, this framework was introduced at the IIT Institute of Design.

At Conifer Research, social scientists and design researchers not only use the 5 E model to unpack complex user experiences, but also as a common platform to closely collaborate with multidisciplinary team members including stakeholders, researchers, designers, engineers, marketers etc.

Constructed as a visualization of experience across locations, time, and platforms, experience mapping captures interactions at each touch point and between transitional stages. It promotes better coordination of cross-platform design and reveals opportunities for new or improved interactions. Although there is little industry consensus over the format and content an experience map should have, some general rules of thumb are worth discussing.

“GO DADA”

An experience map would work well when it is both documentary (photo-illustrated) and descriptive (diagrammatic with notations). With a flair of Dadaism, which incorporates factual photomontage to reflect the realism of which painting is not capable, an illustrative experience map with clear visual communications of user stories captures fleeting behaviors and the transitions in between.

A good experience map should also be visceral, reflective of people’s emotional responses. When and where are people frustrated? Have their emotions changed over time and in different spaces? What delights them? By investigating both the behaviors and emotions of consumers, the experience map allows deeper understandings of how and why the observed activities occur.

TEMPORAL

An experience map depicts how people experience a product, service, marketing message, or environment over time. A good experience map is temporal and focuses on a continuum of activities rather than on any particular moments. It helps connect complex human behaviors and uncovers opportunities that might have otherwise been omitted or offered in isolation. These allow stakeholders, who are often compelled to prioritize differently to understand one another’s needs and to better collaborate.

By going beyond the individual points of interactions across time, experience mapping equips the research team with the ability to “zoom in” to examine detailed issues as well as to “zoom out” for broader perspectives.

For instance, a client was interested in developing new products to help families in emerging markets combat mosquitoes at night and ensure a good night of sleep. By reconstructing the entire user experience temporally, the research team discovered that preparing for a good night of sleep involves behaviors and strategies beyond evening routines.

SPATIAL

A useful experience map should also be spatial. Paying attention to transitional behaviors across

space often helps reveal unmet affordances. What drives people to adopt the same product across different spaces even though it's meant to be used only in one environment? A cleaning product that is designed specifically for toilet bowls may be used on kitchen sinks. Therefore, there is opportunity to collaborate across different departments.

Figure 3, sample experience map that uses layers of photos and text to depict multiple steps, spaces, and emotional changes across the experience.

ACHIEVING A UNIFIED UNDERSTANDING OF CONSUMER BEHAVIORS THROUGH EXPERIENCE MAPPING EXERCISES

Although the above rules of thumb provide a structural basis for an experience map, how to construct it collaboratively into a unified vision within an organization deserves further discussion. There are several principles to follow.

DEFINE THE RIGHT EXPERIENCE TO MAP

The right experience should not be too narrow or too broad. One tip is to think about the ultimate goal that people try to achieve through their actions. For example, one experience map exercise was framed as taking care of the home instead of bathroom cleaning. To truly understand consumer experiences, one must initiate the analysis session with a clear and strong focus on consumers and their behaviors, rather than on potential business solutions.

FACILITATE KNOWLEDGE SHARING

The experience mapping exercise provides opportunities to break down organizational barriers. It allows research team members from different

disciplines to connect by creating shared knowledge together. Although it is natural that different platforms (home cleaning vs. pest control) innovate within their own organization, experience mapping demands that a research team come together, beyond organizational barriers. It helps team members to communicate and focus on behavioral patterns among all participants at different stages of their experience.

Engage stakeholders

Invite stakeholders to participate in the analytical session. It fosters consensus within the organization as it allows the stakeholders to connect with real customers and collaborate with the team. The shared ownership as well as understandings of customer insights help stakeholders make informed strategic decisions.

Keep teams small and intimate

Rather than having one person facilitate in front of a large audience, it's more effective to organize an experience mapping exercise in a small team setting of 3-5 people, to allow for a more "intimate" and collaborative work environment. The most collaborative group session functions like a beehive, where many "honeycombs" of small teams composed of researchers, designers, marketers, and engineers are busy working together and contributing their expertise. When teams are small, people are more willing to engage and contribute.

Prepare a draft experience map to kick-start

To save time and provide a reference point for the team, supply raw sketches of what the user experience may look like. Avoid presenting a finished map, no matter how nice it looks, to an audience that was not involved in creating it or asking if they agree with what they see. People may refrain from giving candid suggestions if they know a lot of time, effort, and money have been invested in what they are seeing. Instead, make plans to build a map from scratch or revise a *draft* map with the team together. The best analytical process demands group participation. To produce pertinent analytical results, all team members should play active roles at group analysis sessions. Assign specific tasks for small teams to work on. Encourage them to work with

others rather than simply criticize what has already been done and presented. Very often, important insights get lost because designers, marketers, and engineers feel they are imposed upon by other people's ideas. Teamwork and an open-minded mentality are fundamental to creating meaningful experience maps.

USE VISUALS

Instead of heavily depending on words, powerful experience maps incorporate pictures and diagrams. Invite designers to participate in the session. They are great resources to ensure better visual communication. A visually compelling experience map helps team members to recall user stories and uncover insights more efficiently. Always scribe notes from group analysis sessions on easel pads. Alternatively, draw cartoon graphics to capture the key points coming out of important conversations. Collective visual knowledge of consumer experiences and routines is easier to understand than words, and helps unify team visions.

CONCLUSION

Design is an iterative process that requires both creative thinking and persistency (Bill Buxton). Though everyday life entails many activities that share characteristics of design thinking (Don Norman), not everyone can be a designer. The duality of genius vs. participatory design is still a popular paradigm among design and research communities. While many value behavioral observations, how to synthesize that data meaningfully into the design process remains an obstacle at the core of participatory design. As a result, ethnographers may feel underappreciated whereas designers may be overwhelmed by anecdotes of user stories documented during ethnographic observation. Instead of looking at overall patterns, designers feel they need to focus on solving specific design problems and to move on to concepts as soon as possible.

To conclude, we reiterate that the experience-mapping exercise is an effective analytic tool. A structural framework, it is tactical and engaging. It helps unify different interests by guiding team members to create something collectively, in this

case, a useful experience map that retells user stories. The timing of when to organize the exercise is important. The experience map is most powerful when created prior to ideation and prototyping. When done properly, it helps interpret human behaviors, and more importantly, it fosters design thinking by uncovering what is missing in these behaviors.

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